

Influence of Creep on Torsional Restraint Provided to Cold-Formed Z-shaped Purlins by Sandwich Panels

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ABSTRACT

Sandwich panels supported by purlins are widely used as the main load bearing part of roof and wall cladding systems of steel buildings. Beside of their main function as building envelope, sandwich panels provide lateral and torsional restraint to purlins which positively influences the member resistance. Lateral restraint provided by sandwich panels is equal for both gravity and uplift loads applied on the panel's surface, however, the torsional restraint may have a different behaviour depending on the direction of loading. While gravity loads increase the contact pressure between the panels and purlins so that the torsional restraint is ensured up to a relatively large rotation of the purlin, uplift loads reduce the contact area which can result in smaller torsional restraint. The paper discusses and compares the different behaviour and addresses the resulting requirements for the experimental setups.

Another aspect that is noticeable in torsional restraint, but not in lateral restraint, is the influence of the materials of the insulation core (usually PUR-, PIR- or EPS-foam or mineral wool) of the sandwich panel. These materials significantly differ in their properties from the materials of faces as they exhibit complex behaviour with time-dependent response. Deformations from compressive stress increase over time which is referred as creep. This behaviour is evident both under gravity loads and under uplift loads, which reduces torsional restraint. Creep of the core can also result in the reduction of the preload force in screws, as the core is under compression after tightening. The paper focuses on the influence of creep on torsional restraint provided to cold-formed Z-shaped purlins by sandwich panels. Results of experimental tests are presented, and the influence of creep is evaluated for various types of the core materials of the sandwich panels.

Keywords: creep, cold-formed purlin, sandwich panel, torsional restraint

1 INTRODUCTION

Sandwich panels have been widely used for roof and wall cladding of buildings. They consist of thin metal faces (flat or profiled) and insulation core. For the core, various materials with suitable properties are used, e.g. polymeric foams, polystyrene or mineral wool. Due to the composition of the panels, the materials are optimally utilized – the faces separated by the core ensure sufficient strength of the panel and protect the core which provides thermal and acoustic insulation and resists shear (1).

In steel building structures, the panels are usually supported by purlins or girts made of hot-rolled or cold-formed members. The latter type of the member is frequently used in modern lightweight structures. Although the primary function of the panels is to provide the building envelope with the required insulation, they might play an important role in stabilizing of the supporting members and

therefore they can positively influence their buckling resistance due to provided lateral and rotational stiffness (2). Proper consideration of this stabilizing effect can result in an economic design of the supporting purlin. The building envelope can partially or fully prevent lateral displacement and/or rotation of the cross-section of the supporting purlin (*Fig. 1*).

Fig. 1. a) Cladding supported by purlins; b) Lateral and torsional restraint provided by cladding

With the exception of lateral deflection of the free flange of a multi-span system, there is no reduction of the member's resistance due to buckling in case of full restraint. But even if only partial restraint is available, certain reduction of resistance may be considered in structural design (3), (4). This can be done using increased values of critical loads (e.g. critical moment M_{cr} in case of lateral-torsional buckling) comprising a certain proportion of the rotational and lateral stiffness. Required formulas can be found in the literature. Minimum required values of the shear stiffness S and rotational stiffness C_D for full restraints are given in EN 1993-1-1 (5) and EN 1993-1-3 (6).

The torsional restraint is characterized by certain value of rotational stiffness C_D which consists of a series of three single rotational stiffnesses in a row: $C_{D,A}$ (rotational stiffness of the connection of the cladding to the stabilized member), $C_{D,B}$ (rotational stiffness corresponding to the cross-section distortion – usually not relevant for common hot-rolled cross-sections) and $C_{D,C}$ (rotational stiffness corresponding to the bending stiffness of the cladding) (2), (6), see *Eq. (1)*.

$$\frac{1}{C_D} = \frac{1}{C_{D,A}} + \frac{1}{C_{D,B}} + \frac{1}{C_{D,C}} \quad (1)$$

While the components $C_{D,B}$ and $C_{D,C}$ are purely a matter of the stabilized member or cladding cross-section geometry, respectively, the rotational stiffness $C_{D,A}$ is influenced by the properties of the connection and by the orientation of the load (7) which results of different distribution of the contact forces between purlin and the cladding. The orientation therefore plays a significant role when investigating the torsional restraint. As the rotational stiffness corresponding to the bending stiffness of the panels $C_{D,C}$ is considerably higher than other components, it can be neglected (6).

For sandwich panels, lateral restraint provided by them to hot-rolled and cold-formed members can be considered for both gravity and uplift load applied to the surface of the panels. In case of the torsional restraint the situation is more complex. The uplift load (typically wind load) applied to the surface of the panel causes reduction of the contact area between the panels and the supporting members which is assumed to result in considerable decrease of the provided rotational stiffness. Conservatively, no torsional restraint might normally be considered. For hot-rolled sections, this simplification should even correspond to reality (8). For cold-formed members certain extent of the torsional restraint might be available. The determination of this torsional restraint (including the definition of a suitable, representative test setup) has been the subject of numerous studies.

Currently valid code for design of cold-formed members and sheeting (6) provides a simple test setup for determining the torsional restraint provided to cold-formed members (here further referred as purlins) by the building envelope, but it does not consider the distributed load applied on the surface of the sheeting and the results may be overestimated (8). It resulted in development of more suitable test setups – Vraný (9) proposed a modification where the support reactions from the distributed load acting on the panel was covered by additional point load applied on the tested cold-formed purlin. A more complex and laborious test setup with distributed load applied on panels was

presented in (10). The experiments were performed with two sandwich panels and two purlins. To introduce torsion, one of the purlins was rotated using a force on lever arm at both ends and the rotational stiffness was calculated using measured displacements of the purlin and magnitude of the applied moment. During the testing, the panels were subjected to distributed load. The research was supplemented by numerical analysis. Parameters for hand calculation of the rotational stiffness were derived. In (11), this test setup was used for series of tests with cold-formed purlins of Z-cross-sections and sandwich panels subjected to uplift load. The tests have shown that practically significant values of rotational stiffness under uplift load can be provided by the sandwich panels. For the investigated specimens, the tests provided almost identical results as tests performed using the setup according to EN 1993-1-3, although the rotational stiffness slightly dropped with increasing uplift load (12). A discussion of the test setups for verification of torsional restraint provided to cold-formed purlins by sandwich panels was brought in (13) together with results of another series of tests performed on a modified test setup with panels under uplift load which was induced using vacuum test method. The rotation of the purlin was performed using a force applied at free flange (as in EN 1993-1-3). Comparable results as in the previous tests were obtained. The European standard for specification of insulation sandwich panels (14) gives test setup for cold-formed purlins stabilized by sandwich panels which is based on the test setup according to (8) with some refinements. Tests performed using this test setup with consideration of uplift load (15) confirm that sandwich panels can provide torsional restraint sufficient for practical structural design. It should be noted that the materials of the insulation core of sandwich panels differs significantly in their properties from the material of the faces (usually thin metal plates). Common polymeric foams used as the core of the sandwich panels exhibit viscoelastic response and material anisotropy due to oriented cellular microstructure of the foam (16). These materials of the core are also characterized by specific time-dependent behaviour which is referred as the creep phenomenon. It is generally characterized by increase of the deformations under constant load in time (1) and strains not proportional to stress (17). It is important especially in case of roof panels with higher magnitudes of long-term load (permanent load, snow) compared to wall panels. This behaviour was observed during experimental tests in the past, e.g. (18). As this specific behaviour applies to the core material, it primarily influences shear strength of the sandwich panels (16) and is especially worth attention in case of sandwich panels with faces of low bending stiffness (flat or lightly profiled faces) (19). Due to complex nature of behaviour of these materials and difficulties in its exact expression (although analytical models have been developing), experimental research is important. Available literature provides some results of tests on the selected core materials themselves or tests on complete sandwich panels under axial or transverse load, however, it should be noted that the research focused on effect of creep on strength and stiffness of the sandwich panels under load. There is still lack of specific information when it comes to the influence of creep on restraining effect of panels on the supporting purlins. It seems that specifically this problem has not been thoroughly studied yet which confirms relevance of the research.

2 METHODOLOGY

2.1 Experimental analysis and specimens

In cooperation with Astron Buildings S.A., series of tests were performed in the testing laboratory of Brno University of Technology, Faculty of Civil Engineering to determine the torsional restraint provided to steel cold-formed Z-purlins by sandwich panels. Three types of sandwich panels were used: panels with profiled external face and polyurethane (PUR) foam core, panels with microprofiled external face and polyisocyanurate (PIR) foam core and panels with profiled external face and mineral wool (MW) core. The inner face was always very lightly profiled, described here as "lined". Cold-formed purlins of the depth 203 or 254 mm and nominal thickness 1.70 or 2.67 mm were used. Cross-sections of the purlins are in *Fig. 2*. The panels were fastened to the purlins using four self-drilling screws per one panel along its width except of the microprofiled panels fastened using hidden fastenings and load distribution clips in both longitudinal joints.

Different setups were used for two completed series of tests of torsional restraints. First setup enabled the application of a distributed load via a vacuum, resulting in a transverse force q_{pur} acting on the purlin (see section 2.2). Although tests for uplift and gravity load were performed with this setup, the distributed load was only applied in the tests for uplift load. Second setup was according to EN 1993-1-3 which basically assumes $q_{pur} = 0$ (see section 2.3).

Fig. 2. A) Cross-sections of the purlins; b) Cross-sections of the panels

For both series, the evaluation was done according to EN 1993-1-3 (6). There the stabilization is modelled via a lateral spring on the free flange. In contrast to the rotational stiffness according to Eq. 1 which is used in the design, the component corresponding to the bending stiffness of panels is neglected in the evaluation using Eq. (2).

$$\frac{1}{K} = \frac{1}{K_A} + \frac{1}{K_B} \quad (2)$$

The combined value of K can be obtained using experimental tests. When a force F is applied on the free flange and δ is the respective displacement, the lateral spring stiffness is given as Eq. (3).

$$\frac{1}{K} = \frac{\delta}{F} \quad (3)$$

The basis for the evaluation was the force-lateral displacement relationship of the free flange established from measured data. The direction of rotation of the purlin during the testing is unambiguously given by the applied load on the cladding (uplift or gravity) and the type of cross-section subjected to torsion moment due to orientation of its principal axes with respect to the direction of load (7), see Fig. 3 (on the left). The test results (combined lateral spring stiffness K) were adjusted using actual measured thickness of the purlin according to EN 1993-1-3. The component K_B expresses the cross-section distortion and is a matter of the cross-section geometry (6). The value of the rotational stiffness of the connection of the purlin and the sheeting is then expressed as Eq. (4) where l_A is width of the tested cladding.

$$C_{D,A} = \frac{K_A \cdot h^2}{l_A} \quad (4)$$

To investigate the effect of creep of the sandwich panel's core the test setup was kept unchanged for certain time and then the entire procedure of testing was repeated. The repeated tests were evaluated using the same manner as the initial tests. The effect of creep can be generally considered as a ratio of the result of the test repeated after some time and the original one. The combined stiffness K obtained from the tests comprises distortional stiffness of the purlin cross-section and stiffness of the connection provided that the bending stiffness of the sandwich panels is neglected. As the distortion is purely a matter of the purlin cross-section geometry, it is not related to the core material which, unlike the purlin, exhibits creep effect. Separated stiffness components K_A were therefore considered ($K_{A,rep}$ from the repeated test, $K_{A,ini}$ from the initial one).

$$c = \frac{K_{A,rep}}{K_{A,ini}} \quad (5)$$

Additional tests on small specimens were performed to investigate the reduction of the preload of the screws over time (section 2.4). Due to tightening of the screws within the assembly, certain stress is introduced to the sandwich panel core and the screws become axially preloaded. It is assumed that this preload will decrease in certain time due to time-dependent effects of the core material. As the restraining effect is assured through the screws, it is reasonable to investigate whether their behaviour is in any way affected by the core.

2.2 Tests of torsional restraint provided by sandwich panels with vacuum chamber

The test setup was based on recommendations given in (8) for panels under distributed load, resulting in a transverse load q_{pur} acting on the purlin. The principle of the test setup is to apply torsional moment on the purlin and measure the applied moment and corresponding lateral displacements of the cross-section to get combined lateral spring stiffness K and to follow the procedure described in section 2.1. The test setup was modified – the torsional moment was applied using a horizontal force at the free flange of the purlin (the scheme of the test setup is in Fig. 3). This modification actually results in test setup close to the one according to EN 14509-2 (14) where this type of the purlin load (force at the free flange) is recommended instead of introducing torsional moment using lever arms at both ends of the purlin. The purlin was equipped with displacement sensors.

Fig. 3. A) Deformation of the purlin under gravity and uplift load; b) Scheme of the test setup

Within one test, two purlins and two panels of a length of 4 m were used. The purlins were supported by a steel frame through fish plates and bearings enabling rotation (greased pins). A vacuum was used for the application of a uniformly distributed load on the panels to simulate the uplift load (11): The tested specimen was placed on a timber vacuum chamber equipped with a vacuum pump. Tightness of the vacuum chamber was ensured by plastic foil passing in between panels and purlins. The rotation of the purlin was performed under four levels of uniformly distributed uplift load applied at the panels: under no uplift and under three consecutive levels where the last one was taken as 80% of tabled load-bearing capacity of the panels for the given span. Actual magnitude of the load was continuously measured using manometer. The test setup can be seen in Fig. 5. Within the tests with mineral wool sandwich panels, additional testing with reverse orientation of the purlin load (corresponding to the gravity load) was performed under no distributed load applied on the panels.

All tests with the test setup for testing under distributed load were repeated after a week. The uplift load was not kept over time (there was only self-weight).

2.3 Tests of torsional restraint provided by sandwich panels according to EN 1993-1-3

In this series tests according to EN 1993-1-3 (6) were performed (test setup is in Fig. 4, testing can be seen in Fig. 5 b)). Displacements of the purlin cross-section caused by the force applied on the purlin flange were continuously measured at its midspan and at both ends of the purlin (similarly as with tests under uplift load).

The tests with sandwich panels with polymeric foam core were repeated after three days ($t \approx 72$ h, two tests) and after a month ($t \approx 720$ h, one test). No load was applied in the meantime. The tests with MW sandwich panels were repeated after a week ($t \approx 168$ h).

Fig. 4. Test setup for verification of torsional restraint provided by cladding

Fig. 5. A) Test setup (sandwich panels under uniformly distributed load); b) Standard test setup

2.4 Tests on reduction of the preload in the screws

For the verification, a piece of sandwich panel of a square shape (0.5×0.5 m) with polymeric foam core was used with purlin fastened using a self-drilling screw at midpoint of the panel (see Fig. 6). Small annular force transducer was placed on the screw to measure its preload after tightening. Total of three tests were performed, the preload was measured for at least 24 hours. The force applied to the screw was recorded with a frequency of 10 Hz for the first 30 minutes of measurement and then with a frequency of 0.05 Hz. In Fig. 6 normalized variations of the measured preload in time are displayed for all performed tests. The most significant drop of the preload occurs within first few hours after tightening and then it stabilizes. As the above-mentioned tests on torsional restraint were always performed several hours after the assembly of the entire system (installation of the measuring equipment and its setting took certain time), it also implies that it apparently does not affect the results of the above presented tests of torsional restraint.

Fig. 6. A) Test setup (test on reduction of the preload in the screw); b) Normalized variation of the screw preload

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Uplift loading

It should be noted that the behaviour of hot-rolled and cold-formed purlins differs significantly. With uplift loading, the cladding lifts off from the hot-rolled purlin ($q_{pur} < 0$), so that one must consider zero torsional restraint (8). Cold-formed purlins tend to rotate under transverse load, which means that the stabilizing torsional moment is transferred via a couple of forces consisting of edge pressure and tension in the screws. For these purlins, this also results in a torsional restraint under uplift load. It can practically only be determined by tests using the force-lateral displacement relationship of the free flange. Examples of typical force-lateral displacement curves can be seen in Fig. 7 for one of the tested specimens (for illustration, curves for load levels 0 and 3 are displayed).

Fig. 7. A) Force – displacement relationship – load level 0; b) Force – displacement relationship – load level 3

The results for uplift load are listed in Table 1 together with calculated ratios c between results from tests repeated after some time and original tests which are further referred as creep coefficients. The values of $K_{A,ini}$ and $K_{A,rep}$ are in N/mm. The ratios were calculated for each level of the applied uplift load. As no clear explicit tendency of the values of these coefficients with change of the load level was observed, the coefficients were averaged for each test. The results show noticeable influence of creep which (in average) seems to be a little greater in case of panels with mineral wool core than for panels with polymeric foam core. However, the difference is relatively small.

Table 1. Results for uplift load (test setup described in section 2.2)

Test No	1		2		3		4		5		6	
Faces (in./ex.)	lined/microprof.		lined/trapezoidal									
Core	PIR		PUR		MW		MW		MW		MW	
Fastening	hidden		direct									
Purlin	Z254 (2.67 mm)		Z254 (1.70 mm)		Z254 (2.67 mm)		Z254 (2.67 mm)		Z203 (1.70 mm)		Z203 (1.70 mm)	
Time	a week		a week		a week		a week		a week		a week	
Load level	$K_{A,ini}$	c	$K_{A,ini}$	c	$K_{A,ini}$	c	$K_{A,ini}$	c	$K_{A,ini}$	c	$K_{A,ini}$	c
	$K_{A,rep}$	[-]	$K_{A,rep}$	[-]	$K_{A,rep}$	[-]	$K_{A,rep}$	[-]	$K_{A,rep}$	[-]	$K_{A,rep}$	[-]
0	58.59	0.926	99.93	1.020	97.01	0.843	113.67	0.898	84.71	0.854	85.10	0.937
	54.24		101.89		81.76		102.03		72.34		79.74	
1	49.96	0.911	149.81	0.848	89.89	0.927	104.09	0.889	94.02	0.737	98.70	0.894
	45.54		127.03		83.36		92.55		69.28		88.28	
2	47.20	0.927	96.05	0.964	77.95	0.913	91.80	0.869	81.03	0.670	90.46	0.860
	43.75		92.55		71.17		79.76		54.27		77.49	
3	50.92	0.938	134.49	0.571	67.03	0.928	82.52	0.906	63.96	0.748	82.13	0.829
	47.77		76.854		62.21		74.74		47.81		68.06	
Aver. c	0.926		0.851		0.903		0.891		0.752		0.880	
Min. c	0.911		0.571		0.843		0.869		0.670		0.829	

Testing under several load levels applied on the panels is crucial especially when uplift load is considered (it reduces the contact area and therefore it influences the restraining effect). Within the

tests, direction of the load applied on the purlin flange was set in accordance with the principle described in section 2.1. The results of the tests according to EN 1993-1-3 (no transverse load q_{pur}) are summarized in *Table 2* together with indication of time the specimens were kept unchanged before repetition of the test. The results of the tests confirm stronger influence of the creep effect in case of mineral wool core. For the polymeric foams, results of the test repeated after a month indicates that the decrease of the torsional restraint after such a long time is small.

Table 2. Results of the tests according to EN 1993-1-3 (test setup described in section 2.3)

Test No	E1		E2		E3		E4		E5	
Faces (in./ex.)	lined/microprofiled		lined/trapezoidal		lined/trapezoidal		lined/trapezoidal		lined/trapezoidal	
Core	PIR		PUR		PUR		MW		MW	
Fastening	hidden		direct		direct		direct		direct	
Purlin	Z254 (2.67 mm)		Z254 (1.70 mm)		Z254 (1.70 mm)		Z254 (2.67 mm)		Z203 (1.70 mm)	
Time	three days		three days		a month		a week		a week	
Direction of purlin load	$K_{A,ini}$	c	$K_{A,ini}$	c	$K_{A,ini}$	c	$K_{A,ini}$	c	$K_{A,ini}$	c
	$K_{A,rep}$	[-]	$K_{A,rep}$	[-]	$K_{A,rep}$	[-]	$K_{A,rep}$	[-]	$K_{A,rep}$	[-]
	56.52	0.985	289.21	0.981	292.71	0.967	197.57	0.764	83.79	0.847
	55.66		283.76		283.17		151.00		70.98	

3.2 Gravity loading

In *Table 3* results of tests of mineral wool sandwich panels with purlins subjected to displacement corresponding to the gravity load (given by the direction of the purlin load) are listed.

Table 3. Results for gravity load (test setup described in section 2.2)

Test No	3		4		5		6	
Faces (in./ex.)	lined/trapezoidal		lined/trapezoidal		lined/trapezoidal		lined/trapezoidal	
Core	MW		MW		MW		MW	
Fastening	direct		direct		direct		direct	
Purlin	Z254 (2.67 mm)		Z254 (2.67 mm)		Z203 (1.70 mm)		Z203 (1.70 mm)	
Time	a week		a week		a week		a week	
Direction of purlin load	$K_{A,ini}$	c	$K_{A,ini}$	c	$K_{A,ini}$	c	$K_{A,ini}$	c
	$K_{A,rep}$	[-]	$K_{A,rep}$	[-]	$K_{A,rep}$	[-]	$K_{A,rep}$	[-]
	137.25	0.779	118.06	0.770	125.90	0.705	134.89	0.826
	106.93		90.93		88.72		111.44	

No distributed load was applied on the panels, therefore no transverse load q_{pur} was acting on the purlins. As the gravity load is assumed to increase the torsional restraint (9), (10), the results of testing under no distributed load can be considered applicable for panels subjected to a certain level of distributed gravity load. The results of the tests according to EN 1993-1-3 are listed in *Table 4*.

Table 4. Results of the tests according to EN 1993-1-3 (test setup described in section 2.3)

Test No	E4		E5	
Faces (in./ex.)	lined/trapezoidal		lined/trapezoidal	
Core	MW		MW	
Fastening	direct		direct	
Purlin	Z254 (2.67 mm)		Z203 (1.70 mm)	
Time	a week		a week	
Direction of purlin load	$K_{A,ini}$	c	$K_{A,ini}$	c
	$K_{A,rep}$	[-]	$K_{A,rep}$	[-]
	129.36	0.852	124.04	0.886
	110.25		109.95	

The different behaviour of hot-rolled and cold-formed purlins is also noticeable for gravity loading, the rotational stiffness and the mechanism changes with increasing rotation. Initially, the stabilizing torsional moment is transferred via contact stress caused by the transverse load q_{pur} introduced by the panel into the purlin. For larger rotations, the moment is transferred via a couple of forces consisting of edge pressure and tension in the screws. The associated drop in stiffness is the reason why according to (14) the rotational stiffness determined from the first mentioned mechanism should be reduced to 75%. Creep due to permanent loads should primarily affect the first-mentioned mechanism. For cold-formed purlins, only the latter mechanism applies, i.e. even with small rotations, the moment is transferred via a couple of forces with tension in the screws. Therefore, creep must also be considered with this mechanism. In (8), creep is covered not by a ratio c , but by a reduction in the modulus of elasticity, irrespective of the type of purlin and the acting mechanism:

$$E_{C,t} = \frac{E_C}{1+\varphi_{\vartheta,t}} \quad (6)$$

where E_C is the mean value of compressive modulus E_{C_c} and tensile modulus E_{C_t} of the core and $\varphi_{\vartheta,t}$ is a parameter depending on the duration of loading (creep coefficient) where t denotes time and is usually given in hours (h). The following therefore applies:

$$c \equiv c_t = \frac{1}{1+\varphi_{\vartheta,t}} \quad (7)$$

In (8), creep coefficients $\varphi_{\vartheta,2000} = 1.29$ and $\varphi_{\vartheta,100000} = 1.83$ for PU and EPS as well as 1.35 and 2.31 for mineral wool are given. They are based on (20). They were determined in tests whose setup reflecting the mechanisms for hot-rolled purlins. The creep coefficients for $t = 200$ h and 1000 h were determined from the tests, extrapolated, and statistically evaluated. Due to the large scatter, this resulted in large creep coefficients for $t = 2000$ h and 100000 h. The mean values measured for 200 h are significantly lower at $\varphi_{\vartheta,200,\text{mean}} = 0.306$ ($c_{200} = 0.766$) for PU and EPS and 0.573 (0.636) for mineral wool. The ratios determined here for mineral wool are somewhat better, but are close to the values resulting from (20). It can be concluded from this that the simplified procedure on which (8) is based, which is identical for hot-rolled and cold-formed members, is justified.

4 CONCLUSION

The paper summarizes results of series of experimental tests focusing on influence of creep of the core of sandwich panels on torsional restraint provided to cold-formed purlins. Significant values of rotational stiffness characterizing the restraint were confirmed in case of all investigated specimens. Obtained values were so satisfactory for the practical purlin design that assumed reduction by the creep effect was not substantially decreasing the benefit. The tests were repeated after certain time period in the same manner to investigate possible time-dependent behaviour and change of the stiffness. It can be concluded that a significant creep effect was found in case of all the tests with substantially different core material. It seems that stronger influence was observed for sandwich panels with mineral wool core. For gravity load, the effect appears to be more significant than for uplift load. Nevertheless, the performed tests indicate that in case of all investigated materials the creep effect is not negligible and should be taken into account in structural design. The results of the tests confirm relevance of the research in the field of time-dependent effects related to the panels with insulation core and their influence on actual behaviour of structures.

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